

RADIOBLOCKS

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Abstract

This milestone describes the benchmarking strategy for the Radio Blocks and demonstrators developed within the RADILOCKS project.

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1 Introduction

In this document we describe the benchmarks we plan to perform for a selection of the Radio Blocks and demonstrators that are under development in WP4 of the RADIOBLOCKS project. The goal is to achieve a coherent benchmarking strategy that allows comparison between existing implementations and implementations that use Radio Blocks as well as comparisons between Radio Blocks that offer similar functionality (even though this overlap is rather limited).

This document was written to reflect a milestone for WP4 of the RADIOBLOCKS project primarily intended for dissemination within the that project. However, we decided to make the document public such that it can be referenced in future project deliverables. It also may be useful to developers the project that want to develop a coherent benchmarking strategy.

1.1 What to measure?

Benchmarks are often defined in terms of operations per second. While throughput is important to know in order to calculate the size of the system needed to process data for a particular instrument, it isn't a fair comparison. An important goal of the RADIOBLOCKS project is to make data processing greener by improving its efficiency, hence it makes more sense to define our benchmarks in terms of energy consumption. We propose to measure the efficiency of our implementations in terms of Joule per input sample. Since power consumption is typically measured in Watt, this can be calculated by dividing by the number of samples per second. This makes it straightforward to compare results between different applications, e.g. a VLBI correlator that uses 2-bit samples with a LOFAR correlator that uses 8-bit samples. For benchmarking individual Radio Blocks the number of bits per sample can be one of the parameters we explore. It is relatively easy to convert this to Joule per bit of input sample in use cases where that is a more appropriate benchmark.

For the Radio Blocks themselves it is sufficient to look at the power consumption of just the accelerators, however, for the demonstrator applications it will also be useful to have an idea of the power consumption of the entire system that runs the application. That would allow a fair comparison with existing implementations that use CPUs or older accelerator technologies.

1.2 The PMT Power Measurement Toolkit

The Power Measurement Toolkit (PMT) [1] is a lightweight, cross-platform library designed to enable accurate power and energy measurements on a wide range of hardware platforms. Developed with performance benchmarking and energy efficiency research in mind, PMT provides a uniform interface for accessing power data from various hardware sensors, including those on CPUs, GPUs, and other accelerators. It supports common monitoring backends such as Intel RAPL, NVIDIA NVML, AMD-SMI, and system-level interfaces like sysfs or external power sensors such as PowerSensor3 [2].

PMT operates in two modes: a measurement mode that records average power consumption over a specific code region, and a dump mode that continuously samples power metrics and stores them with timestamps for post-analysis. This allows users to collect high-resolution power profiles or compute energy usage associated with particular parts of an application. PMT's architecture is designed to minimize overhead, using background sampling threads and caching mechanisms where applicable.

By offering consistent and programmatic access to energy data, PMT makes it possible to incorporate energy-to-solution and power efficiency into benchmarking efforts. This is particularly valuable for evaluating trade-offs in performance-portable or GPU-accelerated applications, where optimizing both runtime and energy consumption is increasingly important. PMT has been used in research and development settings to support sustainability-aware benchmarking and to provide deeper insights into the energy characteristics of modern compute workloads.

2 Radio Blocks

2.1 Filter module

The filter is a new GPU library that contains an efficient Poly-Phase Filter bank implementation. In addition, it optionally applies phase and amplitude corrections to the data (in particular: fractional delays and bandpass correction).

2.1.1 What to measure?

We will measure the performance (in terms of operations per second and number of input samples per second) and energy efficiency (in terms of operations per joule and number of input samples per joule). We will measure the (approx-

imate) percentage of time spent in FIR filtering, performing FFTs, other corrections, and the final transpose.

2.1.2 How to measure?

We will use the internal benchmark program that comes with the library.

2.1.3 What parameter space to explore?

The parameter space is huge due to the large number of configuration parameters, so we only vary the number of channels (at least all powers of two between 16 and 256). We will assume a sufficient number of antennas and a sufficiently high sample rate to keep the GPU busy.

2.1.4 What accelerators to explore?

We will perform the tests on a Grace Hopper system and on a Blackwell GPU (the RTX PRO 6000 Blackwell, or any newer device).

2.1.5 What to compare against?

We will compare the new filter against some older code that is similar to what is currently being used by the LOFAR correlator.

2.2 VLBI delay module

The VLBI delay module converts 2-bit samples to floating-point and applies the fine-grained delay correction. Since VLBI data is (typically) provided as 2-bit samples, multiple samples can be packed into a single byte. This reduces the bandwidth needed to move samples into GPU memory and read them into GPU registers. As a result the delay module still has to apply the final part of the integer delay correction to select the right sample within a byte. The module also applies the fractional delay correction by doing a (real to complex) FFT, applying an appropriate phase shift and doing an inverse (complex to complex) FFT. Finally fringe rotation is applied by applying an appropriate phase shift followed by a conversion back into real samples. More details on the algorithm can be found in section 2.1 of [3]. All these steps can be combined efficiently in a single GPU kernel.

2.2.1 What to measure?

We will measure the amount of energy needed to process a single sample expressed as Joule per sample for a single accelerator.

2.2.2 How to measure?

We will add an internal benchmark program to the Radio Block and plan to use the PMT Power Measurement Toolkit to measure the power used by the accelerator while running that benchmark.

2.2.3 What parameter space to explore?

The only real parameter in the VLBI delay module is the size used for the forwards and backwards FFT used for correcting a fractional sample delay. The whole point of having a separate delay module is to decouple this FFT size from the FFT size that dictates the output spectral resolution of the correlator in order to choose a smaller value that allows more frequent model updates. So we do not need to explore very large FFT sizes. And to avoid FFT-artifacts it is not advisable to use very small values. Therefore we will restrict measurements to the following parameter space:

- Number of frequency channels between 32 and 512; only powers of two are necessary.

2.2.4 What accelerators to explore?

Since this is a Radio Block that is specific to the VLBI correlator, benchmarking will be done on the same set of accelerators as for the VLBI correlator demonstrator as detailed below.

2.2.5 What to compare against?

Comparing the performance of this Radio Block against the existing CPU implementation in the SFXC CPU correlator is not trivial since the CPU correlator integrates the functionality of this Radio Block with the VLBI filter Radio Block. We will rely on the benchmarking of the VLBI correlator demonstrator to get an idea about the efficiency of this module compared to the existing implementation.

2.3 Window-Overlap filter module

This Radio Block implements the filter that converts real-valued floating-point samples from the time domain into the frequency domain, and transposes them into the format required by the Tensor Core Correlator. This is done using optionally overlapped windowed FFTs ("WOLA") to improve spectral fidelity. Specific details on the WOLA algorithm can be found in section 2.2 of [3].

2.3.1 What to measure?

We will measure the amount of energy needed to process a single sample expressed as Joule per sample for a single accelerator.

2.3.2 How to measure?

We will add an internal benchmark program to the Radio Block and plan to use the PMT Power Measurement Toolkit to measure the power used by the accelerator while running that benchmark.

2.3.3 What parameter space to explore?

VLBI science cases exist for both small and large number of frequency channels. The module currently supports non-overlapped, overlapped top-hat window and overlapped Hann window modes. Adding support for additional window functions is trivial but should have no real impact on performance as it just means multiplying the samples with a different number. So testing more window functions makes little sense. Therefore we will restrict us to the following parameter space:

- Number of frequency channels between 32 and 16k; only powers of two are necessary.
- Non-overlapped, overlapped top-hat window and overlapped Hann window modes.

2.3.4 What accelerators to explore?

Since this is a Radio Block that is specific to the VLBI correlator, benchmarking will be done on the same set of accelerators as for the VLBI correlator demonstrator as detailed below.

2.3.5 What to compare against?

Comparing the performance of this Radio Block against the existing CPU implementation in the SFXC CPU correlator is not trivial since the CPU correlator integrates the functionality of this Radio Block with the VLBI filter Radio Block. We will rely on the benchmarking of the VLBI correlator demonstrator to get an idea about the efficiency of this module compared to the existing implementation.

However since this Radio Block provides similar functionality as the Filter module, we will try to compare the performance of this Radio Block. To facilitate this comparison we will make sure there is sufficient overlap in the accelerators we will use to benchmark this Radio Block.

2.4 Tensor Core Correlator

The Tensor-Core Correlator [4] is a GPU library that performs the actual correlations on GPU tensor cores. This library is further developed as part of the RADIOBLOCKS project.

2.4.1 What to measure?

We will measure the performance (in terms of operations per second) and energy efficiency (in terms of operations per joule).

2.4.2 How to measure?

The library comes with an internal benchmark program that measures both the performance and energy efficiency. It also tests the correctness of the computed correlations.

2.4.3 What parameter space to explore?

We will test the performance for the input types that are (or will be) supported: 4-bit and 8-bit integers, as well as 4-, 8-, and 16-bit floating point, and for all numbers of receivers up to 576. Other parameters (such as the integration time and the number of channels per band) will be fixed to reasonable defaults (to 768 and 256, respectively) to limit the parameter space.

2.4.4 What accelerators to explore?

We will perform the tests on a Grace Hopper system and on a Blackwell GPU (the RTX PRO 6000 Blackwell, or any newer device).

2.4.5 What to compare against?

Unfortunately, there is no high-performing alternative anymore that makes a fair comparison possible. We used to benchmark the TCC against xGPU (developed by NVIDIA), which was previously known as the fastest GPU correlator, but xGPU does not work on the Hopper or newer architectures. As TCC is much faster, xGPU is not maintained anymore.

2.5 Tensor Core Beamformer

The Tensor Core Beamformer is a high-performance GPU implementation of digital beamforming, designed for real-time processing in radio astronomy and medical ultrasound imaging. At its core, it uses the ccglib library [5], a generic and reusable tool for complex-valued matrix multiplication on modern GPUs. The library supports multiple precisions and backends, including tensor cores on NVIDIA GPUs and matrix cores on AMD GPUs.

In radio astronomy, the beamformer primarily operates in FP16 precision to achieve high throughput at reduced energy use. In medical ultrasound imaging, it demonstrates flexibility by using INT1 precision for binary matrix operations.

The application is well-suited for benchmarking as it combines high computational intensity with practical constraints on performance, accuracy, and energy efficiency. Its use of accelerator features makes it a representative workload for evaluating modern GPU platforms beyond AI domains.

2.5.1 What to measure?

We aim to measure both performance and energy efficiency. Primary performance metrics include throughput (e.g., beams per second or GFLOP/s) and kernel execution time. For energy efficiency, we measure total energy-to-solution and average power consumption during execution. Secondary metrics may include memory bandwidth utilization and tensor/matrix core utilization.

2.5.2 How to measure?

Performance will be measured using internal timing (e.g. CUDA events) and validated with external profilers when appropriate. Energy measurements will be collected using the Power Measurement Toolkit (PMT).

2.5.3 What parameter space to explore?

We will systematically explore the following dimensions to characterise performance for LOFAR-like workloads:

- **Input matrix sizes:** Matrices corresponding to LOFAR stations, ranging from a few to several dozen input fields and up to several hundred beams per station (e.g., 100–1000), reflecting typical observations where multiple Tied Array Beams (TABs) are formed.
- **Numeric precision formats:** FP32, FP16 and FP8, to evaluate the impact of reduced precision on performance and efficiency.
- **Kernel tuning parameters:** Tile sizes for tensor core operations, thread/block configurations, and memory transfer strategies that affect GPU occupancy, bandwidth utilisation, and computational efficiency.

We will include realistic LOFAR configurations extracted from existing observations, ensuring that the parameter space covers both representative synthetic workloads and real-world scenarios.

2.5.4 What accelerators to explore?

We plan to benchmark on:

- NVIDIA GPUs with Tensor Cores (e.g., GH200, RTX 4000 Ada)
- AMD GPUs with Matrix Cores (e.g., MI200 series, Radeon Pro W7700)

Optionally, CPUs with AVX-2 or AVX-512 for baseline comparisons. These platforms cover different architectural approaches to matrix acceleration and expose the effect of hardware-specific features on energy and performance.

2.5.5 What to compare against?

We will compare:

- Different precisions within the same accelerator
- ccglib (tensor core-accelerated) versus other implementations (e.g., cuBLAS, rocBLAS)

Comparisons will be framed in terms of throughput, latency, energy-to-solution, and compute efficiency (e.g., GFLOP/s/W).

3 Demonstrators

3.1 VLBI Correlator Demonstrator

3.1.1 What to measure?

For the VLBI correlator the most important metric is probably the amount of energy needed to process a sample expressed as Joule per sample for a single accelerator. Since power consumption is typically measured in Watt, this can be calculated by dividing by the number of samples per second. The number of samples per second that a single accelerator can process is interesting in its own right since it determines the number of accelerators needed to reach a certain throughput. The EVN also operates in real-time mode, so a certain minimum throughput has to be reached.

3.1.2 How to measure?

We will use the PMT Power Measurement Toolkit, possibly in combination with the PowerSensor3.

3.1.3 What parameter space to explore?

- Number of stations between 4 and 32; at least all powers of two in between these values should be explored.
- Number of frequency channels between 32 and 8192; only powers of two are necessary.

3.1.4 What accelerators to explore?

As the Radio Blocks that build up the VLBI correlator are only available on GPUs we can only benchmark the correlator on systems with a GPU. Given the wide range of parameters that are relevant for this application it makes sense to consider a wide range of GPU systems. Therefore we plan to benchmark the following classes of systems:

1. Low-end workstation/server GPU.
2. High-end workstation/server GPU.
3. Edge-computing device with integrated GPU and unified memory.

4. Unified/hybrid GPU server system.

At this moment the following systems are available to us in these categories:

1. NVIDIA RTX A4000 GPU, NVIDIA RTX 4000 Ada Generation
2. NVIDIA A100 GPU
3. NVIDIA AGX Orin system
4. NVIDIA GH200 system

However since the RADIOBLOCKS cluster is still in the process of being built and will be populated with newer generation GPUs in the near future, we may decide to change the list of accelerators to run the benchmarks on.

In addition to this we intend to establish if there are any power savings that can be achieved by using RDMA and GPU-direct technologies by comparing power consumption when the correlator is configured to use those technologies with a configuration that uses the regular TCP/IP stack and explicit copies between main memory and GPU memory.

3.1.5 What to compare against?

The current EVN correlator is a CPU-based correlator. Therefore we should compare the performance of the VLBI correlator demonstrator against this CPU-based correlator. Ideally we would compare the power efficiency based on measurements of the power usage of the complete system. For practical purposes we will exclude the power usage of the storage systems and external network switches, since those components will be part of both the GPU correlator and the existing CPU correlator. We will include the power usage of the integrated switches of the chassis that holds the blade servers as these switches will not be part of the GPU correlator.

3.2 COBALT, the LOFAR correlator

Currently, the LOFAR stations, network hardware, and correlator/beam former (also known as COBALT), are being upgraded to enable simultaneous low-band and high-band observations. Both the COBALT hardware and software are upgraded. The “corner turn” (a redistribution of data across the network) was part of COBALT itself, but after the station upgrade, the data will be redistributed on the way from the stations to COBALT, to reduce the costs of network equipment

and the amount of data transport. Also, both the COBALT correlator and beam-forming software pipelines are improved and optimized through the use of the radio blocks developed in this project.

In the D4.6 deliverable, we will report on the performance of the COBALT correlator on the new COBALT hardware, in terms of the number of LOFAR stations supported, the observation bandwidth, number of samples per second processed, network bandwidth use, and the number of number of operations per second that are performed by the key signal-processing steps (filtering, correlators, beam forming). This will be compared to the performance of the previous COBALT correlator. We will also measure if there is sufficient GPU idle time to lower the GPU clock frequency; this makes the GPU run slower (which is fine as long as real-time constraints are met) and, up to some optimum, more energy efficient.

3.3 The AARTFAAC correlator

The AARTFAAC correlator correlates the samples from 576 individual LOFAR low-band antennas in the core area to create 1-second all-sky images. The AARTFAAC correlator runs independently from the COBALT correlator, and has fewer features (e.g., no source tracking as it always points at the zenith, and no beam-forming observations), but its data rates are higher than that of COBALT. The AARTFAAC and COBALT correlators do share common software components (the *radio blocks*).

Based on experiments with the RADIOBLOCKS cluster, we will acquire a (separately funded) GPU cluster, for continuous AARTFAAC observations. In the D4.6 deliverable, we will report on the performance of the AARTFAAC correlator, in terms of the maximum number of antennas supported, observation bandwidth, network bandwidth use, number of samples per second processed, and operations per second. This will be compared to the previous AARTFAAC correlator. We will verify if, and to which level we can stretch the system performance beyond its minimum requirement of correlating 576 dipoles at 30 MHz bandwidth. In addition, we will measure or estimate the energy use, to determine the energy efficiency of the system.

4 Conclusion

The benchmarking results will be published in deliverable D4.6 as part of showcasing the various demonstrators. We also expect to present the benchmarking

results as part of other dissemination efforts, such as presentations at relevant conferences and future papers on the radio blocks.

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